

MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

CP17: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_1F_535-621_87_MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_2F_2-1774_1773_+1_iteration_2

MS peptide 17 Se
CP17

CP18: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_1F_535-621_87_MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_2F_2-1774_1773_+1_iteration_9

MS peptide 18 Se
CP18

CP16: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_1F_535-621_87_MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_2F_2-1774_1773_+1_iteration_10

MS peptide 16 Se
CP16

MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071

CP24: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071_3F_828-1001_174_MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071_2F_218-1567_1350_-2_iteration_11

MS peptide 24 Se
CP24

CP23: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071_3F_828-1001_174_MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071_2F_218-1567_1350_+2_iteration_1

MS peptide 23 L
CP23

MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151

CP63: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_1F_1222-1311_90_MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_3F_33-1415_1383_+2_iteration_3

MS peptide 63 L
CP63

CP64: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_1F_1222-1311_90_MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_3F_33-1415_1383_-1_iteration_5

MS peptide 64 FLStWPCPD
CP64

CP65: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_1F_1222-1311_90_MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_3F_33-1415_1383_-1_iteration_6

MS peptide 65 LStW
CP65

MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291

-1 (3a2→2a1)

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-1 (2a1→1a2)

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rRNA
7,119

CP88: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291_2F_3056-3259_204_MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291_3F_3120-3197_78_-1_iteration_5

MS peptide 88 B
CP88

CP89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291_2F_4808-5617_810_MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291_1F_4921-5037_117_-1_iteration_29

MS peptide 89 PhC
CP89

MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341

CP91: MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341_3F_1059-1172_114_MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341_1F_1-1620_1620_-2_iteration_9

MS peptide 91 W
CP91

CP90: MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341_2F_2501-2623_123_MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341_3F_2298-2531_234_+2_iteration_3

MS peptide 90 L
CP90

MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461

CP99: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461_3F_438-596_159_MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461_2F_170-715_546_-2_iteration_17

MS peptide 99 BSeW
CP99

CP100: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461_3F_438-596_159_MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461_2F_170-715_546_-2_iteration_18

MS peptide 100 BWPCPD
CP100

CP98: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461_3F_438-596_159_MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461_2F_170-715_546_+2_iteration_6

MS peptide 98 B
CP98

MtrunA17_MTg0490471

CP149: MtrunA17_MTg0490471_2F_422-538_117_MtrunA17_MTg0490471_1F_220-1740_1521_+1_iteration_16

MS peptide 149 N10N14FLSe
CP149

CP148: MtrunA17_MTg0490471_2F_1031-1147_117_MtrunA17_MTg0490471_1F_220-1740_1521_+1_iteration_7

MS peptide 148 Se
CP148

MtrunA17_MTg0490971

ncRNA
6,062

CP151: MtrunA17_MTg0490971_2F_476-628_153_MtrunA17_MTg0490971_1F_277-534_258_+1_iteration_0

MS peptide 151 W
CP151

CP150: MtrunA17_MTg0490971_2F_1562-1699_138_MtrunA17_MTg0490971_3F_1542-1727_186_+1_iteration_12

MS peptide 150 St
CP150

Supplementary Dataset S4. Eight primary-source transcripts associated with multiple PRF events. Chimeric peptide models (CPs) and corresponding MS peptides (bottom) are shown together with transcript models (top) that feature the transcript type, length in nucleotides, and relative positions of ORFs (to scale) involved in the production of CPs. Reference ORFs (refORFs) and reference proteins (refProts) are shown in yellow. Alternative ORFs (altORFs) and alternative proteins (altProts) are shown in pink. The first in-frame start codon (AUG) in each refORF is marked with a green triangle. Codes of CPs modeled with MS-supported altProts are shown in bold. Codes of CPs with “confident” MS peptide detection in at least one sample are underlined. Transcript models also show the positions and characteristics of PRF events, which are mapped with an asterisk. The description of a PRF event should be interpreted as follows. For example, CP88, -1 (3a2→2a1): a minus 1 frameshift changes the translation from frame 3 to frame 2, which corresponds to the change from altORF2 to altORF1. An altORF1 in this study is defined as the one that starts earlier than an altORF2. Throughout this study, unique numbers are assigned to chimeric models and their matching chimeric MS peptides. MS peptide identifiers also contain codes of biological samples in which they were detected. For example, the chimeric MS peptide of CP65 was identified in leaves, stems, and the whole plant. Thus, the identifier of MS peptide 65 ends with “LStW”.